

ISSUES IN TEACHING SPEECH IN KOREAN LANGUAGE

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Annotation: This article presents issues of speech activity and communication. In the study of speech activity, it was established that almost every speech utterance contains speech phenomena that are not provided either by the language system, or by the norm of language, or by applications. This article examines motivational sentences in Korean and the imperative and inviting forms that lead to motivational sentences. This fact allows syntactic science to solve current problems of communication and cognition. The question of the sentence and its appearance, the features of syntactic connection, has various solutions in the study of modern Korean language. The reason is that theoretical issues of syntactic analysis are associated exclusively with the study of simple and complex sentences, determining the ways in which different parts of the sentence interact. A sentence is a unit of communication, its semantics and structural composition, created by standard features and standard grammatical models.

Key words: speech activity, communication, speech act, normalization, Korean language.

1. Introduction

Currently, the teaching of the Eastern language in Uzbekistan is represented by two components - university and lyceum (lyceums and colleges), in particular, Eastern languages are studied in lyceums and schools in order to continue studying in a higher educational institution.

The problem considered in this article is obvious, since profound changes in social, political, and economic life have a great impact on the development of the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan. One of the most important manifestations of this process is the steady trend towards the use of pedagogical technologies in teaching a foreign language, in particular Korean. The education system is faced with the task of preparing students for cultural, professional and personal communication with representatives of countries with different social traditions, social structure and linguistic culture.

The correct organization of educational activities is implemented taking into account the needs of the students themselves in mastering the spiritual riches of people by setting them an educational task, the solution of which requires experimentation with the material. The teacher's task is to help students become subjects of learning activities, i.e. determine your own goals, choose means, adjust, evaluate, and take responsibility for your actions and results. In this case, the teacher will be helped by relying on the student's individual activities. In accordance with this approach, the center of learning is the student as a subject of activity. It follows from this that the purpose of classes and ways to achieve it should be determined from the position of the student himself, based on taking into account his interests, needs, and individual characteristics.

The educational process should be based on joint educational, productive activities, during which there is a gradual increase in the functions of students at all stages of training.

2. Korean linguistics within existing directions

In the circle of the humanities, linguistics plays a particularly important place. The nature of interdisciplinary relations, the mutual influence of these sciences and linguistics largely determined the strategic directions of language learning, established the type of correlation of tradition and innovation in the history of linguistic teachings. The first reflections on the language were recorded already in

the ancient Indian treatises of the 5th-4th centuries BC. Antique thinkers (Heraclitus, Agustite, Democritus, Aristotle, etc.) posed and partially addressed the philosophical issues of language.

They were interested in the problems of naming, the connection between thought and speech, the relationship between lexical and grammatical semantics, the theory of anomalies and analogies, and the questions of the origin of the language. Along with the philosophy of language, ancient scholars actively studied the grammatical structure of the language (Alexandrian and Pergamon grammar schools). Roman grammars were created on the model of the Greek, rhetoric issues were solved (Mark Terence Varron, Ely Donat, Priscian, etc.).

Modern linguistics is facing not only the future. Many of its ideological ties are associated with traditional linguistics, since it concentrates the scientific energy of linguistic ideas of previous eras, the energy that stimulates the search for new approaches to language.

Korean foreign (Russian-speaking) linguistics has been actively developing since the beginning of the 20th century and is represented by the works of E.D. Polivanov, A.A., Kholodovich, Yu.N. Mazur, L.R. Kontsevich and others. For the first time in 1925-1930, E.D. Polivanov in his article talks about the relationship of the Korean language with the languages of the Altai family.¹ Scientific studies have shown that issues in Korean linguistics are dealt with in different ways. Of great importance are the scientific studies of Korean scientists Seo Jung Soo, Nam Ki Sim, Guo Young Geun, Kwon Jia Il, Park Young Song, Yom Song Mo [서정 수1996: 50-69]. System descriptions of the grammatical structure of the modern Korean language are reflected in the works of A.A. Kholodovich, G. Ramstedt, Yu.N. Mazur, L.B. Nikolsky, L.R. Kontsevich, S.E. Martin and others, whose feature is the priority of synchronous descriptions, a subjective understanding of the structure of

¹ Polivanov E.D. On the relationship between the Korean and "Altai" languages. News of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR. VI series, 21: 7 (1927), 1195-1204.

http://www.mathnet.ru/php/archive.phtml?wshow=paper&jmid=im&paperid=5514&option_lang=rus

the language, taking into account the knowledge accumulated in the process of pedagogical activity [Rudnitskaya E.L. 2013:5-20].

During the formation of the Korean grammar tradition, the role of universal grammars was quite deep: undoubtedly, the problem of terminological adequacy as a completely required analysis². The transitional stage from universalism to the description of the idiomatic nature of Korean grammar is reflected in the writings of Yu Gil Zhong and Kim Gyu Sik, who managed to illuminate the interaction of the principles of universalism and idiomaticity in grammatical theories.

The actual use of language in communicative situations (M. M. Bakhtin, S.I. Vinogradov, T.G. Vinokur, O. B. Sirotinina, etc.) and the study of the communicative nature and structure of the language from the standpoint of the patterns of organization of speech communication, rationing and the functioning of language in society (V.M. Alpatov, T.V. Arutyunova, etc.) determined the formal-semantic structure of linguistic nature.

In the 20th century, as in world linguistics, Korean linguistics affirms the tendency to use “objective” methods of language research, which require to exclude as much as possible the imposition of categories alien to it borrowed from other sciences (schools of linguistic structuralism). In addition, the principles of mathematical thinking (mathematical linguistics, linguistic statistics, computer / computational linguistics, machine translation, etc.) are being introduced. Recently, more and more prominent place in modern Korean linguistics is occupied by such linguistic objects as linguistic activity and products of linguistic activity, especially communicative linguistics. However, communication and speech activity, becoming

² 서정수. 국어 문법. 서울: 한양 대학교 출판 원, 1996. -- 1568 p. (So Jong Su. Grammar of the mother tongue. - Seoul: Hanyang University, 1996); 남 기심, 고영근. 표준 국어 문법론. 서울: 탑 출판사, 2004. -- 461 p. (Nam Ki Sim. Guo Yong Gyn. Theory of normative grammar of the native language. - Seoul: Thap, 2004. - 461 p.); 박 영 순. 한국어 문장 의미론. 서울: 박이정, 2001. - 338 p. (Park Young Song. Theory of the semantics of sentences in Korean. - Seoul: Pakichon, 2001. - 338 p.); 염 선모. 국어 문장 의미 의 연구, 경북대 박사 학위 논문. 서울: 경북대 1985. - 150 p. (Yom Song Mo. Research on the semantics of the Korean language sentence. - Seoul: Gyeongbuk University, 1985. - 150 p.).

objects of study in linguistics, put forward a number of tasks that need to be addressed. These are issues of speech activity not in a narrow understanding (psycholinguistic), but in a broad sense: linguistic means in the processes of generating speech and its understanding in discourse and text. This position can be expressed by the formula presented by us:

$$\textit{Speech activity} = \textit{language (norm)} + \textit{speech}.$$

Language is presented as a system and as a norm. The language system defines the language material of the system - the grammar of the language (rules for the compatibility of elements). The grammar of the language, in turn, includes the means and rules of communication.

The speech includes the usage and the actual speech, where language material and speech acts (communication processes) are considered - speech material (texts). The end result is real conversion.

Language in this correlation of the components of speech activity is a knowledge of the system of means and rules of speech thinking (think speak and understand) fixed in the linguistic consciousness. Paraphrasing E. Coseriu³, we can say that language is an ideal system of means of language elements (units) and the corresponding classes of language elements (units) that provide the potential for speech-interpretation acts: the norm is what and how to or should be said; and speech is the realization, actualization of the potential capabilities of the language system in the process of communication (real communication, speech acts and texts as products of speech thinking).

Since real communication may differ from customary ways of speak, as they usually say, between the norm and the speech act (text) an intermediate link is distinguished - the usage (a kind of generalization of specific speech acts and texts,

³ E. Coseriu in 1960-1970 was president of ELO (European Linguistic Society (lat. Societas Linguistica Europea, SLE) - an international scientific community that unites linguists from mainly European countries and contributes to the development of linguistic research in Europe and beyond. [1] Founded in 1966, the first Andre Martine was president and has held annual conferences gathering up to several hundred participants since 1968. The company has published linguistic journals *Folia Linguistica* and *Folia Linguistica Historica*).

an unconscious and uncodified norm). When speech is perceived, the selected links (language - norm - usage - speech) correspond to the scheme "an ideal system of means, realizing the ability to understand the message - how to understand - how nice to understand - the real perception of the message."

All components of speech thinking are in certain relationships: the system and the norm belong to the language, the usage and the actual speech acts - speech; norm and usage are brought together by their "normalization". The norm consists of speech models adopted and traditionally used in the corresponding ethnolinguistic collective (such a definition of the norm is close to the definition of a language by A. Gardiner⁴). Indeed, a norm as a set of rules for the implementation of a language system and a system of such rules turns out to be connected with both the language and the external conditions for the generation of speech. In this sense, the norm "serves as a filter that distributes the capabilities of the system (while providing some choice within limited limits) for specific speech acts depending on specific (typical) situations." In other words, the norm governs the use of elements, structures, models of both the language system and the speech system. In that regard, it acts as part of the system. The further development of the norm theory is associated with the concept of variance, independent of whether we follow the triad of E Coseriu "systems - norm - speech", where the norm as correlates of the system limits the variation inherent in the latter, or we follow the concept of the Prague Linguistic School, where the norm represents how system of mandatory manifestations of the

⁴ Sir Alan Henderson Gardiner (Eng. Sir Alan Henderson Gardiner; March 29, 1879, Eltham, Greenwich, London - December 19, 1963, Oxford) - English Egyptologist and linguist.

He made a great contribution to the theory of the Egyptian language. He created "Egyptian Grammar: An Introduction to the Study of Hieroglyphs" to this day remains the standard reference grammar (manual). Based on the achievements of representatives of the Berlin Egyptological School: Adolf Ehrman and Kurt Zeta, Gardiner systematized knowledge of the Egyptian language and published in 1927 Egyptian Grammar, combining exhaustive grammatical material with accessible explanations and study assignments.

Gardiner took an active part in creating the fundamental "Berlin Dictionary of the Egyptian Language". Considering the interpretation of Egyptian texts to be one of the main tasks of Egyptian philology, he published and commented on many valuable monuments. His study of Egyptian "onomasticon" (see the Ramesseum Onomasticon) made it possible to determine the meaning of many Egyptian words, and also made a great contribution to the study of the historical geography of Ancient Egypt. In addition to being the author of special Egyptological works, Gardiner is also the author of original works on general linguistics.

language (ideal invariant) in speech (in the form of a real version). Thus, the norm, on the one hand, and on the other, in a certain sense, is subject to variability as a necessary condition for its own development.

The buffer link between the norm and the speech act is the usage (uncodified norm). By being elements of speech activity, language, norm, usage, speech constitute the object of linguistics. Between the components of speech activity there is a functional relationship, which can be represented as follows:

Table 1. Speaking practice

<i>Speech situation(speech)</i>	<i>Speech act</i>	<i>Usage</i>
		<i>Norm</i>
	<i>Speech act</i>	<i>Language system</i>
		<i>Norm</i>
		<i>Usage</i>

The diagram shows that the generation of the statement (speech) is determined, on the one hand, by the language system and the norm and usage superimposed on it, and on the other hand, completely independent of the language and not controlled by the speech situation. In studies of speech activity, it was found that almost every speech statement contains such speech phenomena that are not provided for either by the language system, or by the norm of the language, or by the usage. These are various kinds of over-phrasal elements of constructing sentences, word combinations, neologisms, etc. if such non-systemic units appear regularly in speech, they can penetrate the usage, and from there move to the norm, which creates real prerequisites for individual shifts in the language system or even to its restructuring.

These arguments are certainly enough to determine as an object of linguistic research not speech or language, but speech activity in its broad sense.

3. Speech activity and incentive targeting in Korean speech

In the modern Korean language sentences of imperative objective (청의문, 명령문) are a special type of communication in contrast to the types observed earlier – narrative (평서문) and interrogative sentences (의의문), as the presence of a status-oriented relationships in conversation performs a leading role. Status-oriented relations are accompanied by grammatical structures in the sentence of imperative objective to specify respectful treatment between the participants of communication – the addresser and the addressee [Pak 2005:287-288].

In the grammar of the contemporary Korean imperative sentences are classified into imperative and invitation sentences [Kim 2018:5-10]. We adhere to this point of view, combining form imperative and invitation mood to sentences of imperative objective type. This decision is connected with the tasks of research – to consider the proposals, which are implemented by the participants of the communication as a call to action and motivation for joint action.

Formal-semantic structure of sentences of imperative objective is that these proposals are used for appellative [Yartseva 1990:80] communication and by nature often do not require reciprocal voice reactions, their purpose is to seek, offer and call to any specific action of the addressee or interlocutor, for example:

A: 어디가 아파서 오셨어요?

B: 배가 아파서 왔는데요.

A: 그럼 여기 이름과 생년월일을 쓰시고 잠깐 기다리세요.

A: *Where is your pain?*

B: *I have a stomachache.*

A: *Write down your name here, date of birth and wait for awhile!*

In the form 기다리세요 – wait formed by attaching to the verb 기다리다 of an affix-marker of the final predicativity of imperative form –세요 the author-sender

is requested to wait. Whether it is perceived by the addressee as the imperative form or as request, can be judged by the speech situation at the moment of action. Given the status-oriented relationship "employee – patient", "staff – user", rather this form is an expression of request from (A). The speech situation at the moment between staff and the patient indicates the respect of the addresser staff to the recipient-the patient. This conclusion follows from the peculiarities of the status of relations in Korean culture and society. Or consider the following dialogue between a grandfather and grandson:

A. 할아버님, 아침마다 운동을 해 보십시오.

B. 그렇게해야겠어.

A. *Grandfather, try to do physical exercise in the morning.*

B. *Yes, it would be necessary to do so...*

In the above dialog, you can specify that the speech addressed to elders – дедушке 할아버님, 해 보십시오 - try, and the source (sender) younger age, as in answer (B) 그렇게해야겠어 is no indication of high respectful social status (age, position). However, you can allow the recipient (B) statement 그렇게해야겠어 – *it would be necessary* is directed toward himself, thinking about his future intentions design –야겠어 (form of obligation 아야/어야/여야 하다 and the future tense 겠), gives the interlocutor (the addressee) their attitude to the statement of the addressee (A).

Thus, the grammatical means of transforming incentive sentences are: a) a predicate in the form of an imperative mood; b) an affix that gives the sentence an incentive; c) incentive intonation. It is noteworthy that in Korean the motivational intonation does not play such an important role as the final motive affix in the predicate. Nevertheless, in order to correctly express a thought, emotional state,

feelings, it is necessary to properly prepare your speech using grammatical means (grammatical categories and forms, service words, interjections, etc.) for expressing various semantic and modal relationships between words as members of a sentence [Kim 2018: 200-215]. Korean sentence of incentive target setting often structurally does not have two components, they lack the subject. The function of the predicate lies in the fact that it appears in all the sentences we have analyzed not only as the main component, but as the main connecting “exponent” in sentences that differ in purpose.

As already noted, a person’s communicative activity is an essential component of his social behavior, therefore, communicative (speech) behavior itself can be considered as part of the national culture. From the point of view of the activity approach, communication is understood as a joint activity of the participants of communication (communicants), during which a common view of the world is developed. It is characterized by processuality, continuity, contextuality. In general, the activity approach better explains the world and is more humanistic.

One of the most common forms of information transfer is verbal communication. This form of transferring information is carried out in the form of texts. Text is a universal tool that can be used both in mass communication systems (text in a newspaper or on television, etc.), and in interpersonal (texts exchanged between communicants). Of great importance for the communicative approach is the introduction to linguistic research of the communicative situation, i.e. set of factors determining the possibility and nature of a communicative act. On the one hand, the communicative situation is always concrete, unique, on the other hand, it is reducible to a certain number of invariants. The structure of the communicative situation includes, according to L. Sakharny, 1) the speaker, 2) what is being said (the subject of communication), 3) the listener, 4) the code (language), 5) the text (implementation of the code), 6) general conditions communication. Communication is influenced by: 1) the setting of the participants in

communication, 2) the nature and purpose of communication, 3) the social roles of communicants, 4) the community of knowledge about the world and language, which awakes in the listener about the same range of ideas that are related to the subject of communication, etc.

Whatever the speech utterance is in terms of volume, no matter how much a person participates in a given communication, in whatever conditions it takes place, it is based on a certain model that is applicable to any type of speech communication. Its scheme includes the following components: addressee, message, context / situation, contact, code, addressee.

In connection with the enthusiasm for this approach, an important and dangerous trend has emerged - the absorption of linguistics by the theory of communication. An indirect proof of this can be found in the emergence of the second half of the twentieth century, several new original theories that were born in line with the theory of communication interest in which linguistics is still great. This is the theory of speech acts, the theory of speech genres, the theory of language games, the theory of intercultural communication. A common thing for them is an active approach to communication and the language as a whole with its idea of the unity of communicative and non-communicative human activity. Each of these theories in its own way solves the problem of personal communication in the social environment, and each of them has its own fate.⁵ Thus, the theory of communication, indeed, absorbs linguistics, which can be observed now. This is not only dangerous, but also wrong, and therefore this process cannot be successful, although it can be quite lengthy.

4. Conclusion

Thus, the practical goal in mastering a foreign language can be formulated and achieved in different ways: it all depends on what specific task is being set.

⁵ For example, the fate of the theory of speech genres was not as successful as the theory of speech acts. Theory of genres created by M.M. Bakhtin in the 1950s (i.e. even earlier than the theory of speech acts), for almost 50 years was unclaimed. But, since the 1970s, there has been a surge in interest in this issue. Today, the theory of speech genres is extremely popular, and it has great scientific potential. The theory of intercultural communication is no less popular.

Solving a practical goal means using a foreign language by students as a means of obtaining new information and exchanging information in the field of their professional activities, as well as application in communication. This approach to learning allows the student, as a future specialist, to rise to a higher level of mastery of his specialty thanks to the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of learning a foreign language.

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